

ReNEW

D4.1 Overall Living Labs Implementation Plan and Management

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

Acronym / Abbreviation	Meaning
4SHIP	4Shipping
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIS	Automatic Identification System
APA	Agência Portuguesa do Ambiente
APDL	Administração dos Portos do Douro, Leixões e Viana do Castelo, SA
CC	Command Centre
CCNR	Central Commission for the Navigation of the Rhine
CEMT	Confederation of European Maritime Technology Societies
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
CO2	Carbon Dioxide
DGRM	Directorate-General for Natural Resources, Safety and Maritime Services
DT	Digital Twin
FMP	Floating Modular Platform
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
GPS	Global Positioning System
GRIWT	Green and Resilient Inland Waterway Transport
HPC	High Performance Computing
IMEC	Interuniversitair Micro-Electronica Centrum
ING	Internationale Nederlanden Groep
ITA	Instituto Tecnológico De Aragon
IW	Inland Waterway
IWT	Inland Waterway Transport
KNT	Konnecta
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LL	Living Lab
MAG	Magellan
MCC	Mobile Command Centre
NOx	Nitrogen Oxides
OHB	Opleidingscentrum Voor Hout En Bouw Vzw
PAN	Panteia
RIS	River Information Services
ROC	Remote Operation Centre
UGAL	Universitatea Dunarea De Jos Din Galati
VHF	Very High Frequency
VTS	Vessel Traffic Services
WP	Work Package
ZES	Zero Emission Services

Table of Contents

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	8
2 INTRODUCTION	9
2.1 LL HIGH LEVEL IMPLEMENTATION PLAN & PREPARATION	9
2.2 MAPPING THE RENEW OUTPUT	11
3 THE LIVING LABS IMPLEMENTATION PLAN.	13
3.1 RENEW IMPLEMENTATION PLAN OBJECTIVES	13
3.2 THE RENEW IMPLEMENTATION PLAN METHODOLOGY	14
3.3 THE RENEW IMPLEMENTATION PLAN TIMELINE	16
4 LL1 - GHENT'S MULTIFUNCTIONAL SYNCHROMODALITY CITY LOGISTICS HUB	19
4.1 CONTEXT-LOCAL PLANS-KEY INITIATIVES	19
4.1.1 VISION AND CHALLENGE TO BE ADDRESSED IN RENEW	21
4.2 EXISTING INFRASTRUCTURE & TOOLS	21
4.2.1 EXISTING DIGITAL INFRASTRUCTURE	21
4.2.2 EXISTING PHYSICAL INFRASTRUCTURE	21
4.3 DATA COLLECTION	22
4.3.1 KPIs	22
4.4 CONSORTIUM STAKEHOLDERS AND THEIR ROLE	23
4.5 USE CASES	23
4.5.1 USE CASE 1: SMART TERMINAL	23
4.5.2 USE CASE 2: FLOATING MODULAR PLATFORM	26
4.5.3 USE CASE 3: ENVIRONMENTAL ALERT SYSTEM	28
4.5.4 USE CASE 4: FLOATING BATTERY SYSTEM	28
5 LL2 - DOURO RIVER WATERWAY	29
5.1 CONTEXT-LOCAL PLANS-KEY INITIATIVES	29
5.1.1 VISION AND CHALLENGE TO BE ADDRESSED IN RENEW	30
5.2 EXISTING INFRASTRUCTURE & TOOLS	31
5.2.1 EXISTING DIGITAL INFRASTRUCTURE	31
5.2.2 EXISTING PHYSICAL INFRASTRUCTURE	31
5.3 DATA COLLECTION	31
5.3.1 KPIs	31

5.4 CONSORTIUM STAKEHOLDERS AND THEIR ROLE	32
5.5 USE CASES	32
5.5.1 USE CASE 1: EXTREME WEATHER	32
5.5.2 USE CASE 2: ILLEGAL WASTEWATER DUMP	33
6 LL3 - PLANNING MITIGATION FOR CLIMATE RESILIENT AND SUSTAINABLE TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE BOOSTING MODAL SHIFT	34
6.1 CONTEXT-LOCAL PLANS-KEY INITIATIVES	34
6.1.1 VISION AND CHALLENGE TO BE ADDRESSED IN RENEW	35
6.2 EXISTING INFRASTRUCTURE & TOOLS	36
6.2.1 EXISTING DIGITAL INFRASTRUCTURE	36
6.2.2 EXISTING PHYSICAL INFRASTRUCTURE	36
6.3 DATA COLLECTION	37
6.3.1 KPIs	37
6.4 CONSORTIUM STAKEHOLDERS AND THEIR ROLE	38
6.5 USE CASES	38
7 LL4 - AUTONOMOUS ZERO EMISSION BARGE	39
7.1 CONTEXT-LOCAL PLANS-KEY INITIATIVES	39
7.1.1 VISION AND CHALLENGE TO BE ADDRESSED IN RENEW	40
7.2 EXISTING INFRASTRUCTURE & TOOLS	41
7.2.1 EXISTING DIGITAL INFRASTRUCTURE	41
7.2.2 EXISTING PHYSICAL INFRASTRUCTURE	41
7.3 DATA COLLECTION	42
7.3.1 KPIs	42
7.4 CONSORTIUM STAKEHOLDERS AND THEIR ROLE	43
7.5 USE CASES	43
8 CONCLUSIONS	45
9 REFERENCES	46
10 APPENDIX-A: USER STORIES	48
10.1 LIVING LAB LL1 - GHENT'S MULTIFUNCTIONAL SYNCHRO-MODALITY CITY LOGISTICS HUB	48
10.1.1 USE CASE SMART TERMINAL	48
10.1.2 FLOATING MODULAR PLATFORM	49
10.1.3 ENVIRONMENTAL ALERT SYSTEM	49
10.1.4 THE FLOATING BATTERY SYSTEM	50

10.2 LIVING LAB LL2 - DOURO RIVER WATERWAY	50
10.2.1 EXTREME WEATHER	50
10.2.2 ILLEGAL WASTEWATER DUMP	51
10.3 LIVING LAB LL3 - PLANNING MITIGATION FOR CLIMATE RESILIENT AND SUSTAINABLE TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE BOOSTING MODAL SHIFT	52
10.3.1 TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE BOOSTING	52
10.4 LIVING LAB 4	53
10.4.1 ZERO EMISSIONS BARGE	53

List of Figures

FIGURE 1. RENEW MULTIDISCIPLINARY APPROACH	10
FIGURE 2. THE INNOVATRIX TOOL	10
FIGURE 3. AGILE LIVING LAB IMPLEMENTATION PLAN.....	18
FIGURE 4. THE GHENT LL CORRIDORS.....	19
FIGURE 5. ONE OF THE OHB BARGES.....	20
FIGURE 6. THE SKIPPER OR THE CAPTAIN NAVIGATING REMOTELY THE VESSEL, FROM THE ONSHORE COMMAND CENTRE	24
FIGURE 7. GENERAL OVERVIEW OF THE MCC, INITIAL DESIGN	25
FIGURE 8. DATASPACE COMPONENTS AND THE LOCAL DIGITAL TWIN. THE GRAPH DEPICTS ALSO THE INTERLINKS OF THE DIGITAL TOOLS WITH THE VARIOUS DATA SOURCES AND MODELS	26
FIGURE 9. CFD SIMULATIONS FOR THE FMP	27
FIGURE 10. DIFFERENT CONTOURS FROM THE CFD SIMULATIONS OF THE FMP	27
FIGURE 11. THE DOURO LL.....	30
FIGURE 12. LL3 AREA.....	35
FIGURE 13. ONBOARD MEASUREMENT SYSTEMS.....	37
FIGURE 14. THE X-BARGE WATERWAY ROUTE TO BE FOLLOWED	40
FIGURE 15. THE X-BARGE PLAN	41

List of Tables

TABLE 1. ADHERENCE TO RENEW'S GA DELIVERABLE & TASKS DESCRIPTIONS	11
TABLE 2. GHENT LL IMPACTS AND TARGET KPIS.....	22
TABLE 3. DOURO LL IMPACTS AND TARGET KPIS.....	32
TABLE 4. LL3 IMPACTS AND TARGET KPIS.....	38
TABLE 5. LL4 IMPACTS AND TARGET KPIS.....	42

1 Executive Summary

The ReNEW project brings together 24 partners from 11 different European nations, each one characterised by different background and expertise in their field, in order to achieve the ultimate goal of assisting transition to a smart, green, sustainable and climate-resilient inland waterway transportation. This report describes the Implementation Plan and Management of the four Living Labs in the ReNEW consortium.

The first Living Lab is represented by Ghent's Multifunctional Synchromodality Resilient City Logistics Hub and will operate in the Belgium inland waterways, starting from Ghent. The second, refers to the Douro Inland Waterway Infrastructure resilience and management in Portugal. The third Living Lab concerns the development of a digital twin application considering the resilience framework within the project as well as mitigation strategies and accounts for international waterways through several countries, such as the Netherlands, Belgium, France, Germany and Austria. The fourth Living Lab prescribes the operation of the innovative and under construction so-called X-barge, to be sailing in Belgium, France, the Netherlands, Germany and the Rhine region. All the aforementioned Living Labs will provide opportunities to test the innovative solutions and tools that will be developed essentially within the framework of WPs 2 and 3, in order to achieve the KPIs determined in WP1. In this direction, physical and digital tools will be deployed.

The purpose of this deliverable was to produce the overall Living Labs implementation plan, and to provide an overview of the Living Labs and what objectives each one aims to attain. To this end, a brief, introductory part is dedicated to the description of each Living Lab and the challenges to be addressed. Next, the existing physical and digital infrastructure is discussed, along with the available and on-demand data. Afterwards, and for each Living Lab, the role of the involved partners and the way of their contribution was defined, however keeping in mind the early stage of the project, as this is the first deliverable in the series of T4.1 deliverables, and the ReNEW approach is fully agile, allowing the continuous evolution of the delivered Living Labs functionalities through the innovations implemented in WP1, WP2 and WP3.

Within the above context an in-depth analysis of each use case is performed, to better explain the vision of the Living Labs and how the involved stakeholders are assumed to benefit from the novel technologies that will be developed. This analysis was assisted by extensive Living Labs workshops using the Innovatrix methodology and tools.

2 Introduction

2.1 LL High Level Implementation Plan & Preparation

This document lays out a detailed and tailored Scoping and Implementation Plan that will be carried out in each of the 4 ReNEW Living Labs (LL) to help meet both the common project objective as well as the LL-specific objectives.

ReNEW is propelled by a core demonstration made up of four actual Living Labs that focus on various facets of Green Resilient Inland Water Transport (IWT). The goal of this core is to create the links required to build creative synergies and develop a thorough contextual approach to a strong and successful future for IWT.

ReNEW aims at overseeing the innovation development process from conceptualisation to commercialization within each Living Lab (LL). To achieve higher levels of innovative maturity, this will entail evaluating interim findings and adding feedback loops. During the proposal preparation stage, the initial ideation phase was already finished, and the results have been included into the descriptions of the LLs.

Each Living Lab (LL) has a specific implementation plan that was created using a multidisciplinary approach and information from a variety of disciplines, including engineering, economics, technology, and inland waterway commerce. The goal is to use an interdisciplinary approach to analyse, synthesise, and create connections between many disciplines to provide cutting-edge knowledge and approaches connected to the project's findings. The end result will be the development of unique Green and Resilient IWT Solutions (GRIWT), which will be used, tested, and improved in the four LLs shown in Figure 1. In addition, the planning and design tasks involve a collaborative process within and between work packages and partners while also relying on information obtained from Living Lab (LL) stakeholders through the assistance of LL leaders and supporting partners. This iterative approach ensures that the planning and design tasks are continuously refined and improved based on input from various sources. In order to more comprehensively identify the needs and requirements of each LL, four distinct 3-hour technical workshops were arranged within the consortium, with substantial participation from various partners from the consortium. During these workshops, significant insights and valuable information were gained regarding the individual use cases of each LL. Simultaneously, the workshops facilitated the mapping of the identified needs with the technologies currently being developed within ReNEW, while ensuring that the project outcomes were always kept in mind. The initial mapping between the needs and the technologies within ReNEW was conducted using a tool entirely developed by IMEC, one of the partners inside the consortium. The methodology around the tool (Innovatrix) aided us in gaining insights as to what, why, who and how

will each LL fulfil the objectives of ReNEW (Figure 2). The knowledge and understanding acquired through these workshops significantly contributed to the production of this document.

Figure 1. ReNEW Multidisciplinary approach

Figure 2. The Innovatrix tool applied within ReNEW

2.2 Mapping the ReNEW Output

The purpose of this section is to map ReNEW’s GA commitments, both within the formal Deliverables as well as the Task description, against the project’s respective outputs and work performed.

Table 1. Adherence to ReNEW’s GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions

Deliverable D4.1 Overall Living Labs Implementation Plan and Management			
Living Labs Implementation Plan.			
Task T4.1 Overall Living Labs Implementation Plan and Management			
Task 4.1 comprises planning & baselining imperatives to establish the overall implementation plan, including key activities per quarter and overseeing project milestones along with key actors and necessary prerequisites. Central to this step is initiating the evaluation of the project’s LLs, including information on the baseline conditions, relevant assumptions to be considered, high level information flows, checklists, and templates, including templates and structure for LL presentations and their associated Deliverables. Associated KPIs and key roles and interactions are clearly defined within this process.			
ReNEW GA Element Title	ReNEW GA Element Outline	Respective Chapter and Description	Document (s) and
ST4.1.1 Living Labs Implementation Plan	Develop the LL implementation plan for adopted scenarios (technologies, resilience and sustainability innovations, digitisation, models and simulation, and decision supported strategies) that (a) integrate innovations and ReNEW initiatives engaging all relevant stakeholders (b) define the integration needs for the operations processes including the Data Space and Digital Twins (c) design the specific elements and connections (d) develop tools for optimal configuration of all components. Once the plan is structured, and prior to Living Labs implementation, it will be presented to the executive board and the Living Labs stakeholders and validated with them in order to ensure its feasibility, and to achieve buy-in and consensus from all partners and maximise its efficiency.		The objectives of this subtask will be covered in Chapters 3,4,5,6 respectively for each Living Lab.
ST4.1.2 Audits and Plan for Transferability	(a) Prepare framework of indicators and criteria so to establish sustainability and replicability and transferability actions, (b) Align Living Labs progress towards capacity building, innovation management and commercialisation. Perform a starting diagnosis, in order to determine the initial site conditions. This would also be important for the evaluation, as well as for the replicability of the project about, the integrated solutions installed and tested at the demo sites.		This subtask and its relevant objectives will be covered in D4.2, a revised version of this document with additional content as depicted in this subtask.
ST4.1.3 Living Labs Implementation Monitoring,	Perform LL monitoring (a) Implement and deploy a monitoring system, (b) develop the executive plans following all previous constraints (c) identify possible limitations of the technologies		This subtask and its relevant objectives will be covered in D4.3, a revised

<p>Validation and Lessons Learned</p>	<p>and innovations to optimize their performances, (d) monitor compliance with existing National and European regulations and policies. Perform LL Validation and Assessment (a) Validate the achievements of the Living Labs with respect to the fulfilment of the objectives of ReNEW (b) assess the performance (c) validate on-site and via simulated use cases the measures of the LL scenarios (d) Perform comparative assessment of the living lab before and after the implemented initiatives (e) Develop outlines for standardisation and replicability and produce the lessons learnt and transferability of strategies and resulting outputs.</p>	<p>version of this document with additional content as depicted in this subtask.</p>
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3 The Living Labs implementation plan.

3.1 ReNEW implementation plan objectives

Task 4.1 is responsible for developing the Living Labs (LL) implementation plan for the use cases of each LL and the introduction of all resilience and sustainability enhancing solutions developed in WP1 to WP3. An important step of the planning process involves the approval of the Living Labs stakeholders, hence, once the plan has been structured, and prior to Living Labs implementation, it will be presented to the executive board and the Living Labs stakeholders and will be validated to ensure its feasibility, and to achieve the buy-in and receive the required consensus from all partners so that it will maximise the implementation efficiency.

The Task 4.1 activities involve the deployment and testing of the related technologies developed, including the information exchanges with the Data Space and the configuration of models, the setup and use of the Digital Twins technologies and the performance of the simulation scenarios for decision and operations support. For each Living Lab, the related project flows involve the steps (a) to integrate the developed ReNEW innovations and to create initiatives engaging all relevant stakeholders (b) to define the specific needs for the operations processes including the Data Space and Digital Twins (c) to design the specific elements and connections (d) and to supervise the optimal configuration of all developed components. Per each Living Lab, the implementation plan involves the following subtasks / implementation objectives:

- **Detailed Design.** Perform detailed LL design and planning, stakeholder’s engagement, licensing and permitting for buildings and operation of the technologies, and iterative detailed LL solutions deployment, including the following steps:
 - *Conduct a Needs Assessment:* Identify the key stakeholders and their needs, as well as the resources required to implement the LLs. This should include identifying the technologies, innovations, and strategies that will be integrated into the LLs.
 - *Develop a Stakeholder Engagement Plan:* Develop a comprehensive stakeholder engagement plan that outlines how the relevant stakeholders will be engaged throughout the LL implementation process. This should include activities for engaging stakeholders at each stage of the process, as well as mechanisms for gathering and incorporating feedback.
 - *Define Integration Needs:* Identify the integration needs for the operations processes, including the Data Space and Digital Twins. This should include identifying the specific components that will be integrated, as well as the connections that will need to be established.
 - *Design Specific Components:* Once the integration needs have been defined, the step involves the design of specific technologies and components, as well as their

- connections, that will be required to implement the LLs. This should include developing detailed design plans, stakeholder engagement plans, also including licensing and permissions.
- *Develop Monitoring and Reporting Mechanisms:* Develop monitoring and reporting mechanisms that will allow you to track progress and evaluate the effectiveness of the LLs. This should include identifying key performance indicators (KPIs) and developing data collection mechanisms.
- **Construction.** Execute LL construction plan in a progressive and iterative mode Customise and configure technology, Resilience and Sustainability use cases, Data Spaces and Digital Twin, simulation and monitoring solutions, including the following steps:
 - *Validate the Plan:* Prior to Living Labs implementation, present the LL implementation plan to the executive board and Living Labs stakeholders for validation. This will ensure that the plan is feasible and achieves buy-in and consensus from all partners.
 - *Implement the Plan:* after the plan validation and approval from the executive board, the implementation will be scheduled and will begin for the ReNEW LLs. This will involve executing the LL construction plan in an agile-iterative mode, involving the implementation development phases, which are described in more detail in the following section as regards their timing, and involve customizing and configuring technology, resilience and sustainability use cases, Data Spaces and Digital Twin, simulation, and monitoring solutions.
 - **Operational Monitoring.** Perform monitoring, Risks management and mitigation, corrective actions, Data Collection for KPIs and reporting. This involves the:
 - *Monitoring and Reporting activities,* performing the monitoring, risks management and mitigation actions as required, the corrective actions, data collection activities and KPIs calculation per use case, and reporting at the Living Lab level to ensure that each LL is meeting the set objectives.

3.2 The ReNEW Implementation plan methodology

The ReNEW implementation plan execution is following an agile approach, the duration of all related implementation activities will be synchronised and interact with the developments in WP1 to WP3 as regards the implementation of the ReNEW Resilience and Sustainability provisions and will communicate with activities in WP5 for the best effect in capacity building, the outreach and the exploitation of the projects' results. The agile methodology approach of ReNEW involves and has been based upon a mixture of SCRUM and KANBAN inspired activities setup.

Inspired by KANBAN ReNEW applies an agile project management framework that emphasizes on continuous delivery and improvement by limiting the work in progress (WIP) and optimizing workflow efficiency. To follow up the project's reporting requirements, the project agile lifecycle has been split in two main reporting phases, where deliverables are aligned to be available in M18 and M36, however,

still there are intermediate milestones that link the project activities and are linked with the project's PMIs following the project's plan towards the implementation objectives.

The Living Labs implementation plan of T4.1, is based on the basic concept behind the Living Labs mechanism in research and innovation projects. That is, it applies all innovations developed in the work-packages WP1, WP2 and WP3 in the ReNEW Living Labs LL1, LL2, LL3 and LL4.

In the Living Labs (LL) approach, KANBAN is used as a methodology for managing the LL execution process in an agile and iterative mode. The LL implementation plan is broken down into small steps, based on the "user stories" which are defined later, and they are a form to express the user needs in the context of an agile methodology. The User Stories are forming the project Backlog, they are prioritized and are added under the KANBAN monitoring process.

The high-level User Stories of the ReNEW living labs were drafted based on the descriptions of the use cases in the next sections. These user stories have been placed in Appendix A, and will be further analysed to processible actions and the development of specific components as ReNEW progresses. The KANBAN based on the User Stories, introduces a board that serves as a visual representation of the overall Living Labs implementation plan and contains columns that represent the different stages of implementation.

- **Backlog:** Represents the pool of User Stories under implementation. It is further explained in the following paragraph, describing the adapted ReNEW Scrum approach.
- **To-Do:** Represents the tasks that are ready for implementation. These tasks are typically representing the tasks implemented via the ReNEW Sprints.
- **In Progress:** Represents the tasks that are currently being worked on. Work in this column is controlled to result to a feasible set of activities within the ReNEW Sprint execution.
- **Review:** Represents the completed tasks for review, the review process is explained in the following paragraph.
- **Done:** Represents the tasks that have been completed and approved.

As tasks move through the different stages of implementation, the KANBAN board is updated to reflect their status. The Living Labs ReNEW teams use Scrum meetings to review progress, discuss obstacles, and plan the next steps. This helps to ensure that the Living Labs implementation is on track and that the work remains focused. The basic methodology concepts adopted from Scrum have been mapped to ReNEW as follows:

- **ReNEW LL Backlog:** A prioritized list of tasks based on the Living Labs requirements that need to be completed.
 - *User Stories:* A simple, high-level description of a feature or requirement that captures the needs of the user and provides a basis for the team to plan and implement the work. The user stories are being listed in the backlog.
 - *Scrum Burn-Down Chart:* A project management graph in the form of a chart that indicates the of work remaining backlog, allowing the development teams to track their progress.
- **ReNEW Sprints:** A fixed period (e.g., 4 weeks) during which a specific set of tasks from the backlog is completed.

- *ReNEW Sprint Backlog*: A subset of the backlog that is for completion during a ReNEW Sprint.
- **ReNEW Sprint Master**: For each LL implementation, the facilitator leading the implementation team, remove any obstacles that may prevent the team from meeting their goals, and ensure that the team is working efficiently and effectively. Typically, the role is played by the **WP Leader** of the corresponding solution implementation.
- **ReNEW Delivery Owner**: The responsible for defining and prioritizing the development backlog during the Living Lab implementation, making sure that the team is working on the right track, and ensuring that the delivered solutions address the needs of the stakeholders. Typically, this role is taken by the **Task Leader** of T4.x (x=2,3,4,5) which corresponds to the Living Labs LL1, LL2, LL3 and LL4.
- **ReNEW Sprint Review and Retrospective**: A meeting held at the end of each sprint in which the team presents their completed work to the stakeholders and receives feedback. This typically coincides with the monthly WP meeting of WP4 performed at the context of each Living Lab, where all solution providers of WP1, WP2 and WP3, are present discussing the progress with the Living Labs Delivery Owners. Further, a 'retrospective' takes places with the end of each sprint in which the teams reflect on their performance and identify areas for improvement.

3.3 The ReNEW Implementation plan timeline

The overall Living Labs implementation of WP4 starts with T4.1 which is the overarching task to this deliverable (D4.1) and concludes on M34. In Month 18 there will be the end of the first cycle, following an agile approach, and for this task there is a follow-up deliverable (D4.2), which will be updated with the progress taking place in the Living Labs tasks T4.3 to T4.6. The final deliverable of T4.1 is at M34 (D4.3).

The implementation plan of the Living Labs involves the general implementation tasks which are described in the following. For each Living Lab, these tasks will be contextualized and become specific to the living lab's needs, following the agile methodology individual steps as described in previous section. For every implementation plan, there has been a 'ReNEW Sprint' assigned, within the same sprint, we can have parallel activities taking place, i.e. plan execution and monitoring.

Implementation Plan Development. (M1-M3)

Develop the LL implementation plan and conduct a needs assessment. Define the technologies, resilience and sustainability innovations, digitisation, models and simulation, and decision-supported strategies that will be adopted. Engage relevant stakeholders and identify integration needs for operations processes, including the Data Space and Digital Twins. Develop tools for optimal configuration of all components.

ReNEW Sprint (1-3, Monthly): Develop the plan, create a backlog of tasks for each. Present the plan to the executive board and stakeholders, collect feedback, and make necessary changes.

Kanban: Refine and update the backlog as needed, update the plan and backlog as needed based on stakeholder's feedback.

Design and plan the Living Lab specific tasks. (M4-M6)

Perform detailed LL design and planning, stakeholder's engagement, licensing and permitting for buildings and operation of the technologies, and iterative detailed LL solutions deployment.

ReNEW Sprint (4-6, Monthly): Plan and design detailed LL solutions in the Living Lab context.

Kanban: Monitor progress, prioritize tasks, and adjust as necessary.

Execute LL construction plan. (M6-M18)

Customize and configure technology, resilience and sustainability use cases, Data Spaces and Digital Twins, simulation, and monitoring solutions. Execute LL construction plan in a progressive and iterative mode.

ReNEW Sprint (6-18, Monthly): Execute the LL construction plan, customize and configure technology, and deploy solutions in iterative mode.

Kanban: Monitor progress, prioritize tasks, and adjust as necessary.

Monitor the Living Lab operations. (M10-M18)

Perform risk management and mitigation and take corrective actions as necessary. Collect data for KPIs and reporting.

Conduct a review of the Living Labs' progress and make necessary adjustments to the LL implementation plan based on the review.

ReNEW Sprint (10-18, Monthly): Perform monitoring, risk management, and mitigation, collect data for KPIs and reporting.

Kanban: Monitor progress, prioritize tasks, and adjust as necessary.

Create the second cycle of LL implementation plan. (M19-M20)

Based on the adjusted implementation plan. Design and plan the second cycle of Living Labs.

ReNEW Sprint: Develop the plan of the second implementation cycle, create a backlog of tasks for each. Present the plan to the executive board and stakeholders, collect feedback, and make necessary changes.

Kanban (19-20, Monthly): Refine and update the backlog as needed, update the plan and backlog as needed based on stakeholder's feedback.

Execute the second cycle of LL construction (M19-M33)

Customize and configure technology, resilience and sustainability use cases, Data Spaces and Digital Twins, simulation, and monitoring solutions.

ReNEW Sprint (19-33, Monthly): Execute the LL construction plan of the second cycle, customize and configure technology, and deploy solutions in iterative mode.

Kanban: Monitor progress, prioritize tasks, and adjust as necessary.

Monitor the second cycle of Living Lab operations. (M19-M33)

Perform risk management and mitigation and take corrective actions as necessary. Collect data for KPIs and reporting.

Conduct a review of the second cycle of Living Labs' progress and make necessary adjustments to the LL implementation plan based on the review.

ReNEW Sprint (19-33, Monthly): Perform monitoring, risk management, and mitigation, collect data for KPIs and reporting.

Kanban: Monitor progress, prioritize tasks, and adjust as necessary.

Living Labs Implementation Assessment. (M28-M34)

Execute the final cycle of LL implementation. Gather the results of the Living Labs operations and take any final corrective actions as necessary. Collect final data for KPIs and reporting.

Based on the above-described steps, Figure 3 shows the overall agile implementation plan per Living Lab. The detailed activities for each Living Lab depend on the specific LL requirements and will be captured in the LL backlog.

Figure 3. Agile Living Lab implementation plan

4 LL1 - Ghent’s Multifunctional Sychromodality City Logistics Hub

4.1 Context-Local plans-Key initiatives

Ghent, the third largest city of Belgium, after Brussels and Antwerp, is located in the Flemish region of the country. One of the main cores of the city’s economy is the Ghent port. However, a significant part of the freight’s transportation is carried out through the city’s canals and rivers (Figure 4). Consequently, the use of barges, accompanied with the relevant necessary infrastructure, plays perhaps the most crucial role in the transportation of goods and people.

Figure 4. The Ghent LL corridors

In that direction, OHB, the local IWT community, has established two City Logistics Hubs, to test out novel synchromodal logistics arrangements. In general, the main purpose of synchromodality, which is a rather emerging concept in Logistics, is the reduction of emissions, costs and delivery times while securing quality of a supply chain. With the ultimate goal of minimizing and, in medium-term, eliminating the emissions from the vessels, the use of low/zero-emission and autonomous barges is definitely a necessary approach (Figure 5). New services and technologies will improve the operational efficiency by lowering the operational costs, enhancing competitiveness and expanding the navigational capabilities. Besides, innovative infrastructure will be deployed as solutions, based on autonomy developments with maturing green options. All these are combined to meet the project’s

utmost objectives: sustainability and resilience of inland waterways through the use of green-centric solutions.

Figure 5. One of the OHB barges

The new infrastructures developed and tested within ReNEW will enable automated navigation and mooring of the vessels, as well as automated loading and unloading, all under the control of a Mobile Command Centre (MCC). At this point, the key idea of exploiting a barge as a “floating battery” and off-grid power supply needs to be highlighted, in order to provide infrastructures, vessels and hospitals with power in times of disaster, when the grid may go down. The infrastructures will be upgraded through the implementation of the following initiatives:

- Create and deliver a robust resilient mobile Smart Terminal, including the Modular Platform and Pontoons, to be used when necessary.
- Development of a Mobile Command Centre (MCC), with shore back-up Command Centre (CC) in Antwerp and Rotterdam, for smart navigation, automated mooring system, loading/unloading activities for the barges.
- The Modular Platform, to be used as a means of transport and a power supply battery in emergency situations as well.
- Installation of sensors for environmental data gathering.
- Autonomous navigation of 3 or more vessels in a platooning configuration.
- New designs and installation of automated mooring systems.

All these are discussed further in the following sections of this chapter.

4.1.1 Vision and challenge to be addressed in ReNEW

Undoubtedly, a prerequisite to achieve the vision of ReNEW for highly resilient inland waterways demands innovations and going beyond the state of the art of the already existing green solutions. To this end, integrating some of the emerging green technologies with advanced, original resilience-assist infrastructure, based on increased autonomy, is required. Particularly, i) autonomous low or zero-emission barges, ii) use of floating platforms, for better maneuverability characteristics, platooning capability and emergency power supply capabilities, iii) several means of transportation of the cargo and people in case of disaster and iv) a shore module with an MCC, including a movable automation control centre, new automated mooring system and a floating pontoon with a modular land ramp are the main solutions to be delivered, to satisfy the scope of ReNEW, as regards the Ghent LL. Nevertheless, it is expected that the outcomes and methodology adopted will be shared with other cities that are of interest for the LL1 inland waterways. Finally, the vision and the results of the Ghent LL contribute to achieving the impact targets set within the project while addressing the 5 common LL value indicators agreed for all the project's LLs

4.2 Existing infrastructure & Tools

4.2.1 Existing digital infrastructure

Given that one urban vessel of OHB already operates remotely by SEAFAR and the second is on the loop, the corresponding digital infrastructure already exists. Particularly, the autonomous ship sends the information to the MCC or to the shore centre of SEAFAR. Besides, some sensors are already installed on the ship, but more are definitely needed.

AIS monitoring system is available. In addition, 4G/5G networks are also available, allowing the exchange of indispensable data for the safe and remote navigability. In that sense, cameras and antennas are also available. In any case, multiple network providers are involved, in order to avoid lack of connectivity. In the worst scenario, with no available network, then the urban vessels are navigated manually by the skipper.

It is easily understood that the digital tools which will be developed by the partners in WP3, will upgrade significantly the existing infrastructure and will aid to a more sustainable and efficient navigation of the barges.

4.2.2 Existing physical infrastructure

Regarding the existing physical infrastructure of LL1, there is a sound infrastructure that ReNEW can further build on. Specifically, OHB already owns 2 urban barges, while one is under construction. Moreover, there is an onshore command centre by SEAFAR to operate remotely the vessels.

4.3 Data collection

For the completion of the work carried out for the use cases of Ghent LL, several kinds of data are needed. Environmental data are probably the most important, since they are directly linked with the resilience and sustainability concepts. Moreover, the data concerning the availability of the vessels (by OHB and SEAFAR) as well as the data for the cranes' location (onshore or on the vessel) and operation, the data for the floating battery and fuel consumption will be manipulated. In this way, the sensors, that will be deployed on the vessel, will absolutely have an essential role, since they are required for the remote operation of the vessel and their autonomous mooring. Additional sensors, camera and hanging equipment for the autonomous crane may also be necessary. All the data collected will be available for further investigation.

Finally, innovation in data management shall be remarked, since it will include smart navigation system with GPS as well as with the use of Copernicus/Galileo for positioning and navigation purposes. Overall, there will be data streaming from LL to the cloud and the Mobile Command Centre.

4.3.1 KPIs

The aimed KPIs in the framework of the Ghent LL, are accordingly described next. Primarily, with the completion of the project, a navigability capacity improvement of 80% is targeted. After all the digital and physical tools are designed, developed and installed, a great increase of 90% of the infrastructure resilience should be remarked, along with a 20% augmentation in modal shift. In addition, a smooth passenger mobility operation will be ensured. Finally, perhaps the most crucial KPI to be met is the drastic reduction of 90% of the IWT environmental footprint, in terms of CO_{2e} emissions. These KPIs are summarised in Table 2.

Table 2. Ghent LL Impacts and Target KPIs

Impacts	Ensure navigability for inland waterways by assuring at least 50% capacity during extreme weather events	Enhanced land/sea/infrastructure resilience to extreme weather and human caused events by assuring at least 80% capacity at network level during the disruptions	20% increase in modal shift	Ensure resilience and smooth functioning of passenger mobility as well as freight transport	Reduce environmental impact [CO _{2e}]
LL1 Ghent	80%	90%	20%	✓	90%

At this stage, recalling the key initiatives for the Ghent LL as presented in section 4.1, it would be useful to attempt to link the initiatives for LL1 with the expected KPIs. Particularly, the deployment of the Smart Terminal and the MCC, along with the installation of several proper sensors onboard, shall contribute to an increased land/sea infrastructure resilience and even to a slight increase in modal

shift. The Modular Platform could assist in smoothing the functioning of passenger mobility, especially during crisis. Finally, the automated navigation of the vessels, in a platooning configuration, enhanced with automated mooring systems, are expected to improve the navigability capacity and definitely reduce the environmental impact.

4.4 Consortium stakeholders and their role

The main stakeholders and the activities to be performed for the Ghent LL, are described below.

Opleidingscentrum Voor Hout En Bouw Vzw (OHB): OHB is the urban barges owner and will participate in the design of the FMP. Overall, OHB will coordinate the implementation, in close cooperation with SEAFAR and UGAL.

SEAFAR: SEAFAR, a well-known remote operator of automated and semi-autonomous urban vessels in Belgium, will provide the remote-control technologies, from onshore control centres, and expertise for increased resilience. They will support the LLs with commercial services and impact pathways. SEAFAR will install their equipment and remotely navigate the vessel from the headquarters in Antwerp. The captain will have in front of him 6-8 monitors (with information and systems but not mobile).

Universitatea Dunarea De Jos Din Galati, (UGAL): The research team from UGAL will design and validate the pontoon and generally the whole structure of the FMP. UGAL will also support the construction and operational activities. A series of technical meetings have already been organized to discuss details about the design of the FMP.

Interuniversitair Micro-Electronica Centrum (IMEC) & Konnecta (KNT): IMEC and KNT will work towards the development of the necessary digital infrastructures. Particularly, local digital twins, dataspace and generic digital twin architecture fall within their contribution to the project. Finally, they are supposed to provide knowledge regarding the operational side and deployment of the tools.

Instituto Tecnológico De Aragon (ITA): Digital twins, dataspace installed for the ReNEW scopes, as well as other tools, will be utilized by ITA to create KPIs for the LL use cases.

In any case, the role of each partner will be highlighted through the following sections.

4.5 Use cases

4.5.1 Use case 1: Smart Terminal

The work carried out in the framework of use case 1, aims to design and build a Smart Terminal, for increased resilience. The objective of the Smart Terminal is to ensure the connection between an

autonomous barge and the shore, on a remote-control way, along with the development of an MCC, to be used under crisis circumstances. The MCC can be considered as a backup with the SEAFAR onshore system in Antwerp. In crisis, it will be deployed and transferred outside of the affected area, within a short time. Consequently, the resilience part for use case 1 will be covered by the fact that the management of the terminal, as a whole, can change within a certain amount of time.

In more detail, the autonomous vessel will send the information needed to the command centre or the onshore centre of SEAFAR, which in both cases will be stored on the cloud. Meanwhile, the skipper or the captain is assumed to perform the management of the vessel navigating it in the river or canal behind a desk in the office. The visualisation of the vessels' routing will most probably be implemented through a dashboard. This process is effectively reflected in Figure 6.

Figure 6. The skipper or the captain navigating remotely the vessel, from the onshore command centre

In order to remotely operate the barge, data must be transferred from the vessel to the onshore control centre and vice versa. The MCC is expected to receive and handle data from a variety of sources, such as from the ship, infrastructure, people and automation-related processes. In the latter case, a remote-control system for a crane fixed onshore or mobile on a vessel is anticipated to be attempted. All these are graphically represented in Figure 7.

Figure 7. General overview of the MCC, initial design

In this context, dataspace and digital twins need to be developed. More specifically, all the different types of data, such as barge data, weather data, as well as other data types relevant to extreme events, i.e., pandemics amongst others, will be stored in a local digital twin. These tools will be designed within WP3. Afterwards, different types of models will be developed and accordingly incorporated in the local digital twin. The local digital twin will act as a decision support tool, both in real time, estimating the short- and long-term impact of climate disaster on the City Logistics Hub, and a what-if scenarios tool, to assess the potential consequences of extreme and cascading effects. In any case, this decision support tool will be used to simulate and create scenarios. Figure 8 shows a high-level overview of the local digital twin and dataspace to be deployed, enriched with all the feasible interconnections.

External stakeholders

Some parties that could be involved in crisis situations management and could exploit all the aforementioned tools are of course the city of Ghent and every relevant city, water authorities, emergency services, governmental institutions public services and crane and logistic operators.

Figure 8. Dataspace components and the local digital twin. The graph depicts also the interlinks of the digital tools with the various data sources and models

4.5.2 Use case 2: Floating Modular Platform

The second use case that will be studied within the Ghent LL is the design of a Floating Modular Platform (FMP). This platform will contribute to the concept of resilience significantly, in a sense that it is expected to be used as an emergency means of transport as well as a power supply source owing to the battery that it will be equipped with, i.e., urban battery. The FMP is practically a floating platform-pontoon, that could be used as a floating battery system or even a floating hospital.

The FMP, as a whole configuration, is considered as a floating pontoon, possibly interacting with the 3 barges of OHB, when needed. Definitely, at this stage of the project, different scenarios are evaluated. Apart from the battery, it will also include automated mooring systems and ramps, perhaps a crane to move containers with freights or remove obstacles. Nevertheless, the new automated mooring system remains a challenge, though an aim of the project, due to its high cost of design and installation. The FMP will work during riotous situations, such as floods and long dry periods, maybe even in case of diseases, thanks to the modular hospital that the pontoon can used as. UGAL, OHB and SEAFAR will closely collaborate to implement a smart navigation system and contribute to the automation of ramp and mooring system. Last but not least, the FMP will assist to the development of autonomous platooning capability for the 3 barges of OHB. It will be designed with the vision to benefit as many entities as possible, since except for the residents of the cities nearby the rivers/canal, rescue public services, logistic providers and crane operators shall also be involved.

As far as the design and implementation of the FMP is concerned, an initial study has already been performed by UGAL. The FMP configuration is slightly different, compared to the one initially conceived. The final one is more flexible and consists of one pontoon and three urban barges, from which two already exist and one is under construction.

From the Naval Engineering point of view, the design and validation of the FMP requires laboured and time consuming processes, like hydrostatic and stability calculations, hydrodynamic numerical simulations (resistance, propulsion, manoeuvrability, ship motions) and strength analysis for several loading cases. The hydrodynamic numerical simulations prescribe mostly the use of CFD codes (for either potential or viscous simulations). These runs will be executed with the use of an HPC and dedicated software, by UGAL. Some initial results of the CFD simulations are shown in Figure 9 and Figure 10.

Figure 9. CFD simulations for the FMP

Figure 10. Different contours from the CFD simulations of the FMP

Given the lack of data for the hydrodynamic and structural behaviours of the urban barges, it is needed to start the calculations with the geometry of one urban barge and then investigate different configurations, for the total formation of one pontoon with ramp, crane and three barges. Even though wave resistance does not exist in rivers and canals, hydrodynamic and hydrostatic calculations must be performed, due to surface ripples of the river. The calculations will be performed for all

configurations, of all speed ranges, also in shallow water, for different loading cases (local and global strength analysis). These results will be validated against experimental ones.

External stakeholders

The FMP will be designed with the vision to benefit as many entities as possible, since except for the residents of the cities nearby the rivers/canal, rescue public services, logistic providers and crane operators shall also be involved.

4.5.3 Use case 3: Environmental alert system

In this use case, some sensors will be installed on the vessels, for environmental data gathering, which will be stored on the cloud and used by the partners. These sensors will provide information about water level, stream, air pollution, CO₂, NO_x emissions. Therefore, in case of alert, the signal from the sensors will be able to raise in time the alarm to government and crisis institutions. Some sensors are already installed on the ship, but particular attention should be paid to those additional sensors that are needed. The data fed back by the sensors are also necessary for the development of prediction models, as demonstrated clearly in the use case 1.

External stakeholders

The most important involved parties are the public environmental services, such as the Flanders Environment Agency (VMM), research institutions and rescue teams as well.

4.5.4 Use case 4: Floating battery system

The study of use case 4 can be decomposed to the two following parts: i) use of batteries for the propulsion of the urban vessel and ii) use of the batteries installed on the vessels, so as the platform can operate as a giant power supply infrastructure.

Regarding the first remark, the barges will be sailing using the power of the electric system combined with an extended battery system. This configuration will eventually evolve into a floating power supply to be used not only in crisis, but also in normal circumstances. The batteries to be installed on the existing vessels and the one vessel being developed, will provide an alternative source of power for propulsion, for a long range. They may be installed either “inside” the barge or on the deck, on top of the barge. It is important to highlight that a combination of both systems can be exploited. For example, when a ship is not sailing, it does not consume power and the available battery can be used for

other purposes. Once again, the autonomous sailing vessels will be deployed with remote control from the MCC.

As earlier in this section mentioned, not only for propulsion, but also as a huge power supply for cascading effects, the battery will be exploited as floating off-grid power supplier (to hospital for example). The use of large battery systems for emergency situations is definitely an overarching goal. The charging capacity of the batteries and generally the energy management system for monitoring the consumption of the fuel, will provide information, available on the cloud, which will be used for the development of several prediction models.

External stakeholders

The most actively involved parties are the public grid network operators, private constructors with need for energy-as-a-service, emergency units and grid back-up systems.

5 LL2 - DOURO River Waterway

5.1 Context-Local plans-Key initiatives

One of the European Union members with inland waterway transportation is Portugal. Since 1990, the Portuguese portion of the Douro River, which flows for 208 kilometres between its mouth in Oporto and the border between Portugal and Spain at Barca d'Alva, has been completely navigable (Figure 11). The Douro is the only inland waterway in Portugal that is a component of the Core Network and the Trans-European Transport Network. With the ability to service the Spanish area of Castilla y León and its logistical hubs like Salamanca, it acts as a link point between the Atlantic Corridor and the North and Centre regions of Portugal. The Douro therefore plays a crucial role in the Core Network. Leixões, one of the main ports of the TEN-T, is connected to the Douro by a short section of shoreline where barges may currently go. Leixões is one of Portugal's major ports and an essential hub for Atlantic marine trade. The ability to enhance freight movements makes this link to Leixões very valuable. To and from the inland ports of Sardoura and Várzea do Douro, the Douro's interior canal is mostly utilised to convey products, notably granite. Yet, the majority of the river's uses are related to tourism and leisure. Following ReNEW's objectives for resilience and sustainability in inland waterways the Douro Living Lab aims at creating means to take actions for both illegal wastewater dumping occurring throughout the river as well as fine-tune the simulation of river behaviour in extreme conditions with the possibility to stand as an example for other use cases.

Figure 11. The Douro LL

5.1.1 Vision and challenge to be addressed in ReNEW

Nowadays, in the Douro region tourism activity outweighs all others, and within this environment, small tourism and leisure activities account for the majority of river use. The Douro Living Lab is envisioned as a blueprint for other use cases in terms of sustainability and resilience and as a future reference for other cities. In order to avoid cascade impacts like congestion, delays, water and energy waste, and increased pollution in the Douro, it is crucial for the LL that the vessels adhere to the pre-approved navigation plan and locking schedules, even in typical operation conditions without weather or infrastructure impediments. There are specific guidelines that all navigation must adhere to in order to guarantee environmental preservation. Although these regulations are supported by the current information systems, they are not yet immediately and automatically enforced. The use cases existing within the Douro LL will be enhanced and complemented by the work in ReNEW in several ways. Starting with developing data spaces for meteorological and hydrological data and adopting their use as a data sharing platform, which will contribute for the improvement of passenger mobility and logistics networks. Furthermore modelling, monitoring, predicting, and acting on extreme meteorological and hydrological situations in Douro and planning the measures required to ensure navigability for inland waterways while considering the resilience and smooth operation of passenger mobility and logistics networks in such events can be achieved with the use of a DT in order to improve the emergency plans already in place. Moreover, in the context of ReNEW and within the vision of Douro LL the potential use of smart contracts is under study as it could automate inland navigation compliance and encourage ecologically responsible behaviour. Finally, the vision and the results of the Douro LL contribute to achieving the impact targets set within the project while addressing the 5 common LL value indicators agreed for all the project's LLs.

5.2 Existing infrastructure & Tools

5.2.1 Existing digital infrastructure

Existing digital infrastructure is already being used in order to achieve the goals of the Douro LL with the vision being to develop and upgrade the existing infrastructure in terms of IT tools, models, as well as implement new technologies available to meet the needs of this LL. Nowadays the Douro LL is able to collect readings from several water related sensors throughout the river and upload them to a near real time information system and then making it available to the public. AIS and RIS data are already in-use providing valuable information for all the vessels navigating through the river. The information system is further enriched with weather forecast data as well as current meteorological data in near real time conditions.

5.2.2 Existing physical infrastructure

In terms of existing physical infrastructure, the Douro LL is already equipped with thirty water level gauges across the river as well as six meteorological stations and four surface water velocity sensors. Furthermore, most vessels are equipped with GPS devices able to broadcast the position of each vessel within the river. Finally, modular inter-modality platforms have the potential to be utilized for seamless transfer of passengers between the river and railway, offering alternative solutions to interconnect the five distinct reservoirs in Douro in the event of prolonged damage to locks or excessively low or high water levels.

5.3 Data collection

Multiple types of data are being gathered and will continue to be gathered within the Douro LL as part of the ReNEW project. Presently, the primary focus of data collection is on water level data obtained through sensors positioned at ten specific locations along the Douro River, as well as measurements of water velocity. Additionally, weather-related data and forecasts are being collected and stored in the information system, while data on the water quality of the river is being collected at frequent intervals. Moreover, geolocation data for each vessel navigating the Douro region is also available and collected via the AIS system.

5.3.1 KPIs

The objective of the Douro Living Lab is to strengthen the region's capacity to survive extreme hydrological and climatic events while also creating strategies and improve the means to preserve

navigability and advance sustainability by monitoring illegal water waste. Through ReNEW the Douro LL will integrate extensive real time data flows by hydrological sensors to develop a digital twin for modelling the behaviour of the river regarding extreme floods and droughts and produce real time predictions. Also, within ReNEW we will investigate the effective use of smart contracts to promote the respect and compliance of Douro inland navigation legislations while protecting the environment. The expected Douro Living Lab impacts and the target KPIs are summarized in Table 3 and will be achieved through the lifecycle of the project.

Table 3. Douro LL Impacts and Target KPIs

Impacts	Ensure navigability for inland waterways by assuring at least 50% capacity during extreme weather events	Enhanced land/sea/infrastructure resilience to extreme weather and human caused events by assuring at least 80% capacity at network level during the disruptions	20% increase in modal shift	Ensure resilience and smooth functioning of passenger mobility as well as freight transport	Reduce environmental impact [CO2e]
LL2 Douro	80%	95%	20%	✓	10%

5.4 Consortium stakeholders and their role

For the Douro Living Lab, the main stakeholder and their roles have been identified as:

Magellan (MAG) is acting as the Living Lab leader of the Douro LL, while closely cooperating with APDL in the whole operation of the LL.

Administração dos Portos do Douro, Leixões e Viana do Castelo, SA (APDL) is considered the main stakeholder, with the need to monitor, alarm and plan actions in the Douro River, considering how it is affected by extreme weather. Furthermore they will be able to provide the means to APA to identify, address and fine the operators that dump illegal wastewater.

5.5 Use Cases

The Douro Living Lab consists of two main use cases that will be studied and developed through ReNEW including the relevant external stakeholders involved in each use case.

5.5.1 Use Case 1: Extreme Weather

A major issue to be tackled with in the Douro region are extreme weather events such as major floods/flash floods or droughts. Addressing the resilience scope of ReNEW these events can impact greatly the efficiency of the operation and the safety of inland navigation. By exploiting the vast real-time data flows generated by the current meteorological and hydrological sensors we will encourage and sustain the creation of a digital twin for simulating river behaviour, particularly for drought and

flood analysis and real-time prediction. This will enable the main stakeholders to go above the limitations of the current meteorological and hydrological models, which lack the adaptability required to respond to what-if scenarios. Furthermore, decision-makers will be able to make smart decisions based on the digital twin of the hydrological river behaviour, especially under extreme weather conditions, that can be also incorporated into the current Emergency Plan. The work within the first use case will complement the existing scenario by developing an innovative method to simulate, detect, predict, and respond to extreme meteorological and hydrological conditions in the Douro, plan the measures required to ensure navigability for inland waterways, and ensure the resilience and efficient operation of passenger mobility and logistics networks in such events, while contributing to building data spaces for meteorological and hydrological data and using them as a platform for data exchange. Thus, helping future data-driven applications emerge, leading to the creation of cleaner and safer transportation networks.

External Stakeholders

Directorate-General for Natural Resources, Safety and Maritime Services (DGRM) is considered as a key stakeholder in taking measures and actions in case of any emergency situation. Furthermore, they are responsible for the ships and relevant equipment certifications regarding tampering risks to sensors and GPS.

Boat Owners & Operator are also considered as key stakeholders in the Douro Living Lab since they are the ones that are either affecting or being affected by the two use cases studied in the Douro Living Lab.

5.5.2 Use Case 2: Illegal Wastewater Dump

The second use case revolves around ReNEW's sustainability goal, with the main objective being the development and testing of systems and solutions to encourage adherence to Douro inland navigation regulations and environmental protection through ongoing monitoring of wastewater deposits in ships to prevent illegal dumping. This will be achieved by utilising smart contracts and blockchain technologies to store wastewater tank levels and the ships GPS position in real time. Furthermore, data such as vessel name vessel position, speed, waste tank capacity, must be gathered, timestamped, and stored in an immutable manner in order for these smart contracts to function properly. Finally, the smart contract will be triggered into execution when a lowering of the tank level of a specific ship occurs outside of a designated wastewater collection area and will issue an illegal dump notice to the ship owner with the corresponding fine.

External Stakeholders

Portuguese Environmental Agency (APA) is considered as the stakeholder with the authority to issue the fines in case of infringements. Furthermore, they are considered as one of the stakeholders that

will be benefited from an automated approach for monitoring illegal wastewater dumping, considering that through data immutability it ensures non-repudiation as well as accountability.

Directorate-General for Natural Resources, Safety and Maritime Services (DGRM) is considered as a key stakeholder in taking measures and actions in case of any emergency situation. Furthermore, they are responsible for the ships and relevant equipment certifications regarding tampering risks to sensors and GPS.

Boat Owners & Operator are also considered as key stakeholders in the Douro Living Lab since they are the ones that are either affecting or being affected by the two use cases studied in the Douro Living Lab.

6 LL3 - Planning mitigation for climate resilient and sustainable transport infrastructure boosting modal shift

6.1 Context-Local plans-Key initiatives

LL3 has been developed specifically to address issues regarding disruptions at terminals, extreme weather events and disruption in the supply chain on the East and South Corridor in The Netherlands, incorporating the Rhombus concept. The Rhombus comprises synchro modal solutions for the waterway system connecting Antwerp, Paris, Liege, Venlo, Nijmegen, and Rotterdam, as depicted in (Figure 12). The Rhombus comprises several canals and rivers, including the Albert Canal, Scheldt-Seine-Meuse, Juliana Canal, and the Waal River, which serve as the primary arteries of the inland waterway system. The recent addition of the Seine Scheldt connection has further expanded this conception of the waterway system, providing an agile concept that allows access to any point during calamities. Governments are strongly promoting modal shift in their policies due to emission reduction objectives, which has a significant influence in reducing traffic congestion. Although inland waterway transportation has not yet reached its full potential, dependability remains a significant problem. Boosting dependability is possible by using information on current water levels, forecasts, obstacles, and traffic on rivers, locks, and bridges, but this rarely occurs. Thus, it is crucial to seamlessly integrate information and planning software and receive proactive advice during the planning process. Within the objective of ReNEW for resilience and sustainability this LL aims at

utilizing an already existing platform “Blue Wave” by extending the platforms capabilities with a planning and mitigation module thus contributing to safe and efficient shipping as well as promoting modal shift targeting to zero emissions.

Figure 12. LL3 area

6.1.1 Vision and challenge to be addressed in ReNEW

LL 3 is envisioned as strategic initiative aimed at achieving sustainability and climate resilience. The Blue Wave platform is designed to be a comprehensive solution that ensures safe and efficient shipping while improving the logistical performance of inland navigation. The platform incorporates a multimodal tool that encourages modal shift and offers strategies to enhance the capacity of resilient infrastructures during disruptive events. It provides real-time and up-to-date insights into the status and progress of transport to various parties involved in the logistics chain, including the skipper, terminal operator, forwarder, and shipper. Users can conveniently carry out their tasks using digital services, thereby enhancing the platform's user-friendliness.

To further enhance the platform's capabilities, a Planning and Mitigation Module will be integrated as part of the Living Lab initiative. This module enables users to plan inland waterway transport and respond promptly to disruptions in real-time. This LL is designed to incorporate and overcome 3 different types of disruptions under the same use case. Disruptions at terminals, disruptions due to

extreme weather and disruption in the supply chain. Resolving these types of disruptions fall within the vision of the LL while the results of the LL will contribute to achieving the impact targets set within the project while addressing the 5 common LL value indicators agreed for all the project's LLs.

The module seamlessly integrates planning services with real-time information about disruptions, providing users with sophisticated mitigation strategies outcomes. The algorithm employed utilizes historical data on past disruptions and the mitigation strategies that were employed to create a knowledge base of problems-solutions adopted in specific conditions and locations. This information can aid in identifying successful mitigation measures implemented previously and provide valuable insights for similar problems in the future. The platform integrates relevant data about waterways in the Netherlands, Belgium, France, Germany, and Austria, combining static and dynamic information about traffic to provide dependable information about the occupancy rate of moorings and waiting times at locks.

6.2 Existing infrastructure & Tools

6.2.1 Existing digital infrastructure

Digital infrastructure is already being used and is planned to be extended in order to achieve the goals set in LL 3. The vision of the LL is to extend the existing platform (Blue Wave) in terms of modularity, as well as implementing new technologies available to meet the needs of this LL. The As-Is situation in LL 3 consist of the Blue Wave platform that is able to stimulate modal shift with a multimodal tool, transport planning services able to improve visibility and reduce costs in the process, A multimodal journey planner for inland navigation, that includes info on inland navigation, rail traffic and road transport, unlocked by multimodal solutions as well as a match-making platform for shippers and barges allowing direct interaction between shippers and barges. The Blue Wave platform will be further enriched with the planning and mitigation module, through this tool users can do planning of inland waterway transport and can act in real-time in case of disruptions. This is made possible by seamless integration of planning services with real-time information about disruptions. The system will provide a sophisticated mitigation strategies advice algorithm. The algorithm will be based on data of all disruptions from previous years and all mitigation strategies adopted. Based on the abovementioned data when a disruption occurs the module will present mitigation measures that were already successfully implemented, which will give the right knowledge for similar problems.

6.2.2 Existing physical infrastructure

Since LL 3 is mainly based on digital solutions to achieve the objectives of the project, the physical infrastructure available is limited only to several types of sensors used already by the platform either inside the vessels (emission, depth measurement, GPS, fuel consumption) or within the area of study. (water level, water velocity, weather stations)

6.3 Data collection

Several types of data are currently being collected and will persistently be gathered within the ambit of LL3 as a component of the ReNEW project. A multitude of sensors have already been deployed within the vessels, allowing for the acquisition of readings pertaining to the velocity of the engine, the consumption of fuel, the loading status, and the navigation data and location of the vessels, as depicted in Figure 13. Furthermore, the bill of loading module provides access to information regarding the commencement and termination of loading operations, as well as the corresponding quantities. Moreover, weather-related data, data from EURIS and AIS data for the vessels in operation are also available.

Figure 13. Onboard measurement systems

6.3.1 KPIs

The objective of Living Lab 3 will be directed towards enhancing and exhibiting a planning and mitigation demonstrator application with the aim of enhancing modal shift towards green inland waterways transport. The module will be part of an existing platform commonly known as Blue Wave. This platform aids in fostering safe and streamlined shipping operations, enhancing the logistical performance of inland navigation, and incorporating methods for augmenting the resilience of infrastructure during times of disruption. These disruptions could arise either from the terminals, due to severe weather or within the supply chain. Following the common impacts set in the scope of ReNEW, below are the Living Lab 3 target KPIs summarized in Table 4, that will be achieved throughout the project life cycle.

Table 4. LL3 Impacts and Target KPIs

Impacts	Ensure navigability for inland waterways by assuring at least 50% capacity during extreme weather events	Enhanced land/sea/infrastructure resilience to extreme weather and human caused events by assuring at least 80% capacity at network level during the disruptions	20% increase in modal shift	Ensure resilience and smooth functioning of passenger mobility as well as freight transport	Reduce environmental impact [CO2e]
LL3	30-50%	50-80%	10%		10%

6.4 Consortium stakeholders and their role

PANTEIA (PAN) is acting as the LL leader while working in close cooperation with 4Shipping on the development of the “Blue Wave” platform as well as the Planning & Mitigation module within the ReNEW project. Furthermore, PANTEIA is providing 4Shipping with the mitigation strategies advice.

4Shipping (4SHIP) is the key stakeholder in the LL as they are the ones developing the Planning & Mitigation module for the Blue Wave Platform.

6.5 Use Cases

Living lab 3 consists of a single use case that was divided into 3 different types of disruption. The first type of disruption concerns disruptions occurring at the terminals. Disruptions at terminals can manifest in various ways, with some of the most common being delays resulting from congestion, limitations in storage capacity, and restricted downstream transport capacity. Congestion at terminals can occur due to a variety of factors, such as an increase in the volume of goods being transported, inadequate infrastructure, or a lack of coordination among stakeholders. Such delays can have significant implications for businesses, as they can result in increased costs, reduced efficiency, and negative impacts on customer satisfaction. The second type of disruption is due to extreme weather events. Extreme weather can have significant impacts on inland waterways transport. Heavy rainfall can cause transshipment stops for goods that require protection from moisture, such as feed and salt. In addition, due to wind, seagoing vessels may experience delays as degassing becomes slower, which can also pose a threat to several goods. Furthermore, strong winds can also lead to crane operation stops, which can further hinder the transportation of goods. Finally, the last type of disruption being considered is disruptions in the transport chain. Disruptions in the transport chain can have significant impacts on inland waterways transport. A common source of disruption is delays in the waterway network, which can be caused by factors such as congestion or maintenance work. Additionally, delays in previous transshipment activities can also cause significant disruptions, as this can also lead to congestion and delays downstream. Moreover, a lack of information about planning from other parties in the transport chain can further exacerbate disruptions, making it difficult to coordinate transportation activities effectively. To comply with the government's emissions regulations, it is necessary to shift transportation modes and reduce road congestion. While inland waterway transport has not been fully exploited, there is a pressing need to

address reliability issues. Although data on water levels, obstructions, and traffic at locks/bridges is available, it is often underutilized in improving reliability. Therefore, it is essential to establish seamless integration between information and planning software and take proactive measures to mitigate the impact of disruptions. Within the scope of ReNEW we plan to extend the functionalities of the Blue Wave platform by adding a planning and mitigation module. This tool enables users to plan and respond in real-time to disruptions in inland waterway transport. Shippers can plan and schedule transshipment timeslots at terminals, while terminal operators can accept requests. Skippers can provide progress updates, including estimated time of arrival. The planning module also provides real-time information on disruptions and waterway status through seamless integration with planning services. To further enhance the platform, a sophisticated algorithm will be added to provide mitigation strategies based on historical data of disruptions and solutions adopted in specific conditions and locations. This knowledge base of successful solutions will be displayed on the platform to offer the right insights for similar problems.

External Stakeholders

Shipper, Terminal Operators and Shipowners will be the demonstrators as They will test the planning mitigation advice algorithm that proposes resilience actions to users in case of disturbances (know-how, datasets, algorithms)

7 LL4 - Autonomous Zero Emission Barge

7.1 Context-Local plans-Key initiatives

The fourth LL of ReNEW project, pertains to the operation of an under construction innovative barge, the so-called X-barge. It will be sailing under the guidance of ZULU Associates, an active initiator, developer and operator in the marine part of IW logistic chains. The X-barge will be sailing from Ghent, Belgium to Duisburg, Germany, through the Netherlands. This entails travelling over waterways that are under the management and jurisdiction of IW authorities of three countries, along with the involvement of CCNR. The whole waterway corridor is demonstrated in Figure 14. The interesting feature of the X-barge, categorized as Class 4 CEMT barge, is its small draft, which will allow the vessel to navigate in low water level rivers without disturbances.

Figure 14. The X-barge waterway route to be followed

With a view to demonstrate and test improved resilience infrastructure, the work to be carried out within LL4 will generally focus on:

- 1) Test, analyse, and present the operational and financial viability of autonomous Class 4 inland cargo barges with alternative propulsion, in relation to climate change
- 2) Acquire the necessary permits for autonomous operation along the use case path in Belgium, the Netherlands, Germany and the Rhine
- 3) Build and evaluate a particular infrastructure
- 4) Increase awareness of autonomous inland barges and social acceptance of them
- 5) Start actual commercial container flows using Class 4 inland barges that are autonomous and have alternative propulsion methods.

7.1.1 Vision and challenge to be addressed in ReNEW

In order to achieve ReNEW's goals and vision, within LL4, for sustainable development of IWT accompanied by increased resilience, there are some crucial aspects that have to be taken into consideration during the design stage (ongoing) of the X-barge as well as its equipment and operation.

First of all, the digitisation of communications between the barges and terminals/operating centres and barges themselves as well, to avoid accidents due to lack of proper systems. Furthermore, autonomy of the vessel dictates the development of relevant AI algorithms. Autonomy of a vessel should include not only its capability to navigate remotely, but also its operation should be feasible without a crew. Next, the alternative propulsion, with use of batteries as energy containers in the aft part of the barge, and hydrogen, is definitely a great challenge to be addressed within the project. The

restricted size of the vessel, in terms of its small draft, is anticipated to increase the efficiency of the terminals, since this kind of vessels are not that much affected by low water levels, in case of extreme dry periods. In that sense, a reduction on size could also increase the redundancy on the logistic chain. Lastly, to attain the demanding targets of autonomous operation, autonomous mooring system, cargo/containers handling, cover energy needs and of course ensure suitable communications, the use of alternative equipment is absolutely indispensable. Some of them, are depicted in Figure 15, where a plan of the under construction X-barge is shown.

Figure 15. The X-barge plan

7.2 Existing infrastructure & Tools

7.2.1 Existing digital infrastructure

4G/5G network on all waterways exists, which enables the data flows, as well as the remote control and operation of the vessel. More digital tools and AI algorithms will be developed by partners and will be elaborated in WP3.

7.2.2 Existing physical infrastructure

Given that the building of X-barge is currently ongoing, there is no specific physical infrastructure available for this LL. Generally, and recalling the international route that the vessel will navigate in, terminals, mooring systems and operation centres for remote control of the vessel do exist. Most of these aspects will be significantly enhanced owing to the ReNEW project. Nevertheless, there are

several parts of the necessary equipment that are missing and need be installed or used. Cameras, radars, sonars for the water depth, wind indicators, AIS, GNSS/GPS and sensors related to equipment or energy are some of them.

7.3 Data collection

For the efficient operation of the autonomous X-barge and its proper loading/unloading, several sources of data are needed. The most typical ones are the location data, data for energy needs, external data concerning sailing conditions (wind, draft, currents etc.), cargo data, handling data. All the data related to the operation of the vessel, will be obtained by means of sensors.

Given that the X-barge is still under construction, a preliminary study needs to be conducted, so as the most suitable design (in terms of its hydrodynamic efficiency, propulsion and resistance and loading of the barge being the most vital parameters) of the vessel shall be determined. Therefore, physical testing of the vessel’s scale model will be conducted, through experiments in a towing tank (Flanders Hydraulic Institute). In addition, numerical, CFD codes will be utilized. The data obtained by each case (experiments and numerical runs) will be used for validity and verification reasons.

Finally, all information related to the fairway infrastructure is available through the relevant IW authorities. For example, information concerning the time that a bridge opens for vessels or whether the locks are working are some indicatives. The data flows are treated by the operation centre, which remotely controls the vessel during its sailing.

7.3.1 KPIs

The aimed KPIs to be achieved in the framework of LL4 are described in this subsection. The use of the X-barge shall demonstrate enhanced navigability capacity in the order of 30-50%, with an accompanied increase in modal shift of 20%. The latter remains an important element, because the modal shift might reduce issues of congestion. However, the most important achievement shall be again the drastic limitation of the environmental footprint, since there will be a 90% reduction of the CO_{2e} emissions. The described KPIs are summarized in Table 5.

Table 5. LL4 Impacts and Target KPIs

Impacts	Ensure navigability for inland waterways by assuring at least 50% capacity during extreme weather events	Enhanced land/sea/infrastructure resilience to extreme weather and human caused events by assuring at least 80% capacity at network level during the disruptions	20% increase in modal shift	Ensure resilience and smooth functioning of passenger mobility as well as freight transport	Reduce environmental impact [CO _{2e}]
LL4 X-barge	30-50%		20%		90%

The continuously developing field of the Class 4 inland barges dictates the testing and analysis of this concept in relation to the environmental conditions, as well as the social acceptance of them and

the acquisition of the necessary permits by the relevant authorities, as already described in section 7.1. Trying to correlate the key initiatives for LL4 with the KPIs, we can state that once these prerequisites are satisfied, the navigability capacity would be increased sufficiently. The automated operation of the barges, equipped with alternative propulsion methods will aid to succeed a significant reduction in CO₂e emissions and possibly an increase in modal shift.

7.4 Consortium stakeholders and their role

As already stated, the X-barge to be used as LL4 is under construction. Therefore, the role of each partner is yet to be clarified and determined. Determined meetings between ZULU Associates and WP2/WP3 partners will be organized promptly, to specify in detail the contributions of each partner. In addition, collaboration with LL1 is envisaged. In more detail, the experience of SINTEF Ocean on autonomous vessels and autonomous mooring will be exploited, while Panteia will assist to different aspects, such as networking opportunities and generally collaboration with LL2 and the partners involved to achieve certain outcomes. Data related issues, such as dataspace, ways to connect cargo information with the barge itself will be addressed to WP3, led by IMEC.

7.5 Use Cases

The purpose of this section is to describe in detail the use case under consideration for the LL 4. In order to attain the vision of this LL within ReNEW, as explained in section 1 of this chapter, the X-barge shall be used. The X-barge is expected to be completed in the second half of 2024. It will operate in a long distance in inland waterways, with a starting point from Ghent, Belgium and ending point the city of Duisburg, Germany. However, this will not be a single trip; intermediate stops will be made. The vessel and the relevant required infrastructure will be used to demonstrate increase resilience and economic viability compared with other moderate, common and overaged used fleets.

The X-barge will be very different from the existing barges. It is designed to carry primarily 24 45-foot pallet wide containers, because this is the most competitive type of cargo. It is designed to be 85m in length and will be distinguished for its hydrodynamic efficiency. It will be equipped with dual electric azimuth thrusters for propulsion and a bow thruster for manoeuvring reasons. In the aft part of the vessel, 3 20-foot energy containers (3x17t) will be placed to provide the vessel with electrical power, while no accommodation infrastructures exist. This fact brings up some advantages such as i) the containers do not mix with the cargo hold, ii) the certification of the vessel is much simpler and iii) easy loading/unloading of the containers. Besides, the distance from the energy containers to the propulsion system is very small, which eventually simplifies the whole system, since no additional cables are needed.

The concept of the X-barge encompasses the ideas of digitisation, autonomy, alternative propulsion and restricted size, in terms of small draft. With enhanced traffic and logistics management (VTS) and appropriate navigation routes and timescales, thanks to the digitization and generally to the digital connectivity between the barges themselves and the barges with infrastructures as well, accidents due to miscommunication (through radio/VHF) will be reduced. Particularly, it will be essential for the communication between the shippers and the Remote Operating Centre (ROC) and perhaps even for the exchange of data between the autonomous ship and the IW authorities.

Autonomy will be an inherent feature of the X-barge. To this end, AI algorithms will need to be developed to ensure the proper, safe navigability of the barge. The AI algorithms will be used initially for planning the voyage from the beginning and after scheduling how the vessels will move during their trip. Moreover, the need to enable decisions making from the vessels itself. Autonomous vessels will be feasible to operate 24 hours per day, while with crew onboard, this time would be considerably reduced.

Alternative propulsion is also a key parameter for the increased resilience of IWT provided by the use of X-barge. The battery owns the primary role in this procedure, with the hydrogen being an aim as well. The batteries will have a dual role: apart from providing power to the barge, they will also be involved in the stabilization of the local grid. The X-barge will use 300KW per hour when operating in normal speed. The recharging time of the battery will be dependent on the infrastructure available. The batteries are supposed to switch when needed. The connection of the batteries is a sensitive parameter, because of the high voltage, which is about 800-1000 V. Therefore, no humans can be involved, in order to eliminate the chances of a fatal accident. Till now, there is not standardized connection. The more ships an operator is running, the lower number of batteries will be needed per ship, which is an important aspect, given the high cost of these batteries (1-1.5 million euros). Wartsila, Zenobe and Corvus are amongst the key providers of marine batteries.

Another important feature of the X-barge is its small draft, which implies that the vessel's operation will not be easily restricted by low water levels, in case of long extreme dry periods. Furthermore, the efficiency of the terminal can be increased by the use of small vessels, since they can sail in smaller canals. Reduction in size may also increase redundancy in the logistic chain.

External Stakeholders

For the structural part, local shipyards will be involved, while for the economical part of the shipbuilding phase, investors and bankers are needed. Except for the structural and economical points of view, there are several parties that will be also involved in the use and operation of the X-barge within a holistic approach. All these are accordingly discussed next.

Through the operation of the X-barge, shippers, who are interested in moving goods fast and in large quantities, will contribute to meet climate ambitions towards zero-emission IWT. They will have the opportunity to improve the public image of their company, by communicating how much reduction of CO₂ their vessels achieve. In any case, for transparency reasons, this has to be clearly proved.

Logistic operators are also involved. Their clients are moving towards sustainable ways for transportation of freights, so it is reasonable that they need to respond. However, a main issue for the increase of the efficiency of the logistics chain is the shortage of crew and, quite often, the overaged crew. Human factor is always a parameter that has to be taken seriously into consideration. In that direction, several problems and accidents are caused due to poor communication through VHF. IW operate around 18 hours. An increase to a 24-hour operation will demand doubling of the crew, which eventually makes the autonomous vessel far more competitive. Therefore, smaller vessels are needed and the minimization of the necessary time for loading is crucial for an efficient logistic chain. In parallel, logistic operators have to come to agreements with the terminals for certain slots. Consequently, it can be easily understood that the role of logistic operators is vital for zero-emission logistics at similar cost with fossil fuel logistics. Finally, in the logistic operators' group, a "load master" can be included. The "load master" will be a person who will inspect the vessel when it reaches the terminal, visionally and physically, will take care of unloading and check what needs to be done on the vessel. In that way the efficiency of the whole process is improved, because the "load master" can do this process for one ship after another, while skippers have a more restricted role.

IW authorities are unfortunately confronted with issues of sustainability. Shippers that are reluctant to change their attitude, crew shortages and obsolescence of the fleet are some of the main problems. To achieve an increase of use of IWT, the authorities have to review the regulations to allow completely the autonomous sailing, because till today, this is performed with exceptions. In that sense an upgrade of their digital and physical infrastructure is vital.

Finally, the energy providers have a unique opportunity to participate actively to the new, upcoming market of alternative energy, since there is an increasing demand for non-fossil fuel energy. However, significant improvements of the infrastructure are needed and specifically well organized and fully equipped locations for the barges to charge their batteries. ZULU have been collaborating with several industrial partners in the field of alternative energy, such as Zero Emission Services (ZES) in Holland, held by Ebusco, ING, Wartsila, and the Port of Rotterdam Authority. As previously mentioned, Zenobe is a battery provider and CMB is a hydrogen provider.

8 Conclusions

The ReNEW project is a research and innovation initiative that seeks to promote resilience and sustainability in inland waterways transport (IWT). The project is driven by a demonstrative core composed of four real-life Living Labs, which are focused on complementary aspects of Green Resilient IWT. These Living Labs are designed to ensure the required interrelations towards achieving innovation synergies and creating a comprehensive contextual approach towards a resilient and thriving IWT future.

The four Living Labs act as distinct areas or regions and are supported by local authorities, involved stakeholders from the inland waterways sector, shippers, boat owners, operators, as well as stakeholders from the inland transport supply chain. The Living Labs follow the common ReNEW implementation process, but each has a distinct ambition and scope on how to approach the goal of resilience and sustainability.

To achieve the goal of resilience and sustainability, a different mix of technologies under a single framework, have been developed in a single optimum adoption scenario for each Living Lab. Specific key performance indicators (KPIs) reflecting the impacts that each Living Lab envisions to achieve are currently being defined. This report provides a preliminary list of these KPIs and lists the technologies/measures of the optimum scenario that will be adopted for their achievement.

Dedicated time plans along with the optimum implementation plans are also under development and will be presented during the next reports. The implementation plans will continue to be updated as the planning and design work becomes more detailed.

As part of the project, the as-is conditions for both physical and digital infrastructure, together with information about existing models, data sets, and tools and key stakeholders, were collected through this report and formed input to the planning and design work of all of ReNEW's activities so far. This information is critical in developing a comprehensive approach to promoting resilience and sustainability in IWT.

The work performed in conjunction with this report includes the framework for resilience and sustainability and all relevant aspects as they relate to Green Resilient IWT, the social dimension and the stakeholder engagements, definition and development of the objectives regarding the DT and Dataspaces technology and use cases, and the Living Labs evaluation framework, including the list of KPIs and assessment methodologies for the impact assessment. Dedicated reports with the outcomes of the work on each of these subjects will be produced in the following months from corresponding Work Packages.

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10 APPENDIX-A: User Stories

10.1 Living Lab LL1 - Ghent's Multifunctional Synchronomodality City Logistics Hub

10.1.1 Use Case Smart Terminal

In the following there are some possible user stories for the Smart Terminal use case.

WHO:	As a vessel owner,
WHAT:	I want to be able to remotely operate my vessel from an onshore command centre,
WHY:	so that I can navigate the vessel from a safe and comfortable location.
WHO:	As a skipper,
WHAT:	I want to be able to access real-time data about the vessel, including its location, speed,
WHY:	and fuel levels, so that I can make informed decisions about navigation and operations.
WHO:	As an onshore control centre operator,
WHAT:	I want to be able to receive and handle data from a variety of sources, including the vessel, infrastructure, people, and automation-related processes,
WHY:	So that I can effectively manage the Smart Terminal.
WHO:	As a crane operator,
WHAT:	I want to be able to remotely control a crane fixed onshore or mobile on a vessel,
WHY:	so that I can perform cargo handling operations without physically being present at the terminal.
WHO:	As a city logistics hub manager,
WHAT:	I want to be able to access real-time data about the Smart Terminal, including weather data, pandemic information, and other relevant data sources,
WHY:	so that I can optimize logistics operations in response to changing conditions.
WHO:	As a crisis management team,
WHAT:	I want to be able to access a digital twin and data space for the Smart Terminal,
WHY:	so that I can simulate different scenarios and assess the potential consequences of extreme and cascading effects in case of a crisis.
WHO:	As a governmental institution,
WHAT:	I want to be able to monitor and control the Smart Terminal remotely,
WHY:	so that I can ensure compliance with regulations and safety standards.
WHO:	As an emergency service operator
WHAT:	I want to be able to access real-time data about the Smart Terminal and surrounding areas,
WHY:	so that I can respond quickly and effectively to any incidents or emergencies that may arise.

10.1.2 Floating Modular Platform

In the following there are some possible user stories for the Floating Modular Platform use case.

WHO:	As the public of a flood-prone area,
WHAT:	I want the Floating Modular Platform to be equipped with a battery and a modular medical emergency equipment,
WHY:	so that it can provide emergency power and medical assistance during flood situations.
WHO:	As a logistic provider,
WHAT:	I want the Floating Modular Platform to be equipped with a crane and ramps,
WHY:	so that it can be used to transport and remove cargo during emergency situations.
WHO:	As an operator of urban barges,
WHAT:	I want the Floating Modular Platform to have a smart navigation system and an automated mooring system,
WHY:	so that it can interact with my barges more efficiently, and economically, and use my barges as a part of solution development for autonomous platooning capability.
WHO:	As a designer of the Floating Modular Platform,
WHAT:	I will provide hydrostatic and stability calculations, hydrodynamic numerical simulations, and strength analysis,
WHY:	so that I can validate the design and ensure that it is safe and effective and be part of the Resilience solution for Urban disaster scenarios.
WHO:	As a user of the CFD codes and HPC,
WHAT:	I want to be able to execute the numerical simulations and obtain accurate results,
WHY:	so that I can provide useful insights for the design and validation of the Floating Modular Platform

10.1.3 Environmental Alert System

In the following there are some possible user stories for the Environmental Alert System use case.

WHO:	As a member of the Flanders Environment Agency,
WHAT:	I want to receive alerts from the environmental sensors on the vessels,
WHY:	so that I can take appropriate measures to prevent or mitigate environmental damage.
WHO:	As a researcher,
WHAT:	I want access to the environmental data gathered by the sensors,
WHY:	so that I can analyse and model trends and patterns in environmental factors.
WHO:	As a member of a rescue team,
WHAT:	I want to receive alerts from the sensors,
WHY:	so that I can be prepared for any emergency related to the environment.
WHO:	As public,
WHAT:	I want to know about any environmental threats in my area,
WHY:	so that I can take necessary actions to protect myself and the environment.
WHO:	As a ship owner,
WHAT:	

WHY:	I want to ensure that the sensors on my vessel are working properly and providing accurate data, so that I can avoid any environmental hazards and maintain compliance with regulations
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10.1.4 The Floating Battery System

In the following there are some possible user stories for the Floating Battery System use case.

WHO:	As an operator of an urban barge,
WHAT:	I want to be able to use an extended battery system along with the electric propulsion system,
WHY:	so that I can have an alternative source of power for propulsion, which will be useful in case of emergencies or even in normal circumstances.
WHO:	As a hospital administrator,
WHAT:	I want to be able to use the batteries installed on the autonomous sailing vessels as a power supply for emergency use,
WHY:	so that I can provide uninterrupted power supply to hospital in case of grid failure or emergency.
WHO:	As a public grid network operator,
WHAT:	I want to be able to monitor the charging capacity of the batteries and the energy management system of the vessels,
WHY:	so that I can manage the energy demand and supply in an efficient manner.
WHO:	As a private constructor,
WHAT:	I want to be able to use the battery system on the urban vessel as an energy-as-a-service provider,
WHY:	so that I can reduce my dependence on the grid network and have a reliable and cost-effective source of energy.
WHO:	As an emergency unit,
WHAT:	I want to be able to use the battery system on the urban vessel as a grid back-up system,
WHY:	so that I can provide emergency power supply to critical infrastructure during power outages or other disasters

10.2 Living Lab LL2 - DOURO River Waterway

10.2.1 Extreme Weather

In the following there are some possible user stories for the Extreme Weather use case.

WHO:	As a river navigator,
WHAT:	I want access to real-time meteorological and hydrological data on the Douro region,
WHY:	

	so that I can make informed decisions regarding the safety of inland navigation during extreme weather events such as floods and droughts
WHO:	As a member of the emergency services team,
WHAT:	I want to be able to access a digital twin of the Douro River behaviour during extreme weather events,
WHY:	so that I can plan and implement emergency response measures quickly and effectively.
WHO:	As a logistics manager,
WHAT:	I want to be able to predict the impact of extreme weather events on transportation networks in the Douro region,
WHY:	so that I can take proactive measures to ensure efficient and safe operations.
WHO:	As a data scientist,
WHAT:	I want to be able to use the vast amounts of real-time data generated by meteorological and hydrological sensors in the Douro region,
WHY:	to develop prediction models that can help stakeholders respond effectively to extreme weather events.
WHO:	As a decision-maker,
WHAT:	I want to be able to use the digital twin of the hydrological river behaviour,
WHY:	to make smart decisions regarding the safety and efficiency of transportation networks in the Douro region during extreme weather events.

10.2.2 Illegal Wastewater dump

In the following there are some possible user stories for the Illegal Wastewater dump use case.

WHO:	As a river navigation authority,
WHAT:	I want to monitor wastewater deposits in ships in real-time,
WHY:	so that I can prevent illegal dumping and protect the environment.
WHO:	As a ship owner,
WHAT:	I want to be able to plan my navigation routes, including locking schedules and overnight mooring sites, and have access to the required services,
WHY:	so that I can comply with the regulations and avoid penalties.
WHO:	As a ship owner,
WHAT:	I want to be automatically charged for the services used and potentially offered certain savings,
WHY:	so that I can streamline my operations and reduce costs
WHO:	As a river navigation authority,
WHAT:	I want to be able to simulate the navigation plan of each ship and execute smart contracts between vessel owners and myself,
WHY:	so that I can ensure compliance with regulations and monitor adherence to the authorised plans.
WHO:	As a river navigation authority,
WHAT:	I want to be able to track real-time data, such as vessel position, speed, engine condition, fuel and waste tank capacity, number of passengers, draught, etc.,
WHY:	so that I can optimise navigation routes and ensure adherence to regulations

WHO:	As a river navigation authority,
WHAT:	I want to be able to issue illegal dump notices to ship owners and fine them accordingly,
WHY:	so that I can enforce regulations and protect the environment.
WHO:	As a port authority,
WHAT:	I want to test certain smart contracts using blockchain technology,
WHY:	so that I can improve the security and dependability of information, supporting the sustainability plans.

10.3 Living Lab LL3 - Planning mitigation for climate resilient and sustainable transport infrastructure boosting modal shift

10.3.1 Transport Infrastructure boosting

In the following there are some possible user stories for the Transport Infrastructure Boosting use case.

WHO:	As an inland waterway transport business,
WHAT:	I want to be able to plan and respond to disruptions in real-time,
WHY:	so that I can improve the reliability of my transport services and to be able to ensure reliable and efficient transportation of goods.
WHO:	As a shipper,
WHAT:	I want to be able to schedule and reserve transshipment timeslots at terminals,
WHY:	so that I can better plan my transport activities and avoid delays caused by congestion and reduce costs.
WHO:	As a terminal operator,
WHAT:	I want to be able to accept scheduling requests from shippers and provide progress updates to skippers,
WHY:	so that I can optimize my terminal operations and to improve my terminal's efficiency and reduce delays.
WHO:	As a skipper,
WHAT:	I want to be able to provide progress updates, including estimated time of arrival,
WHY:	so that stakeholders can adjust their plans accordingly, and all clients can be informed of the status of their cargo.
WHO:	As a user of the Blue Wave platform,
WHAT:	I want to be able to access real-time information on disruptions and waterway status,
WHY:	so that I can plan and respond to disruptions effectively and to make informed decisions about transportation planning.
WHO:	As a user of the Blue Wave platform,
WHAT:	I want to be able to access a knowledge base of successful solutions to disruptions in specific conditions and locations,
WHY:	so that I can quickly and effectively mitigate disruptions when they occur.
WHO:	As a user of the Blue Wave platform,
WHAT:	

WHY:	I want to have access to a sophisticated algorithm that provides mitigation strategies based on historical data of disruptions and solutions adopted in specific conditions and locations. so that I can effectively respond to disruptions and minimize their impact.
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10.4 Living Lab 4

10.4.1 Zero Emissions Barge

In the following there are some possible user stories for the Zero Emissions Barge use case.

WHO:	As a shipper who values sustainability,
WHAT:	I want to utilize the X-barge to transport my goods in a way that reduces CO2 emissions,
WHY:	So that I can communicate the environmental benefits to my customers and improve my company's public image.
WHO:	As a logistics manager,
WHAT:	I want to incorporate the X-barge into our transportation strategy,
WHY:	so that we can take advantage of the benefits of digitization, autonomy, and alternative propulsion, and reduce the risk of accidents due to miscommunication.
WHO:	As an IWT Intelligent Solutions Provider,
WHAT:	I want to provide, configure, and test algorithms for the X-barge that ensure safe navigation and decision-making,
WHY:	so that the barge can operate autonomously for 24 hours per day, reducing the need for crew and increasing efficiency.
WHO:	As an IW authority,
WHAT:	I want to review regulations and infrastructure to enable the operation of autonomous vessels like the X-barge,
WHY:	so that we can meet climate ambitions towards zero-emission IWT and increase the efficiency of the logistics chain.
WHO:	As a shipper of goods,
WHAT:	I want to utilize the X-barge to transport my products in a fast and efficient manner while also contributing to reducing carbon emissions in the transportation industry and I want to be able to communicate the CO2 reduction achieved by using the X-barge,
WHY:	to improve the public image of my company and show my commitment to sustainable practices and because it is important to me that there is clear and transparent evidence of the reduction in CO2 emissions to maintain credibility with my customers and stakeholders.
WHO:	As a regulatory authority for inland waterway transportation,
WHAT:	I am aware of the challenges faced by the industry in terms of sustainability, crew shortages, and obsolescence of the fleet. Therefore, I am reviewing the regulations to allow completely autonomous sailing and upgrading the digital and physical infrastructure to support the increased use of autonomous vessels.
WHY:	This will improve the efficiency of the logistics chain and promote sustainable transportation at similar costs to fossil fuel logistics.
WHO:	As an investor or banker,

<p>WHAT:</p>	<p>I want a financial business model to analyse the construction of the X-barge that represents a promising opportunity for sustainable transportation and economic viability,</p>
<p>WHY:</p>	<p>so that I can successfully invest to a technology that can contribute to the development of a more environmentally friendly and efficient transportation industry and earn a return on my investment/</p>
<p>WHO:</p>	<p>As a logistic operator,</p>
<p>WHAT:</p>	<p>I want to minimize the time required for loading and unloading of vessels, therefore, I am exploring the possibility of hiring a “load master” who can inspect the vessel upon arrival at the terminal, take care of unloading, and check what needs to be done on the vessel, while the skippers have a more restricted role,</p>
<p>WHY:</p>	<p>so that I can improve the efficiency of the logistics chain and reduce costs.</p>
<p>WHO:</p>	<p>As a logistic operator,</p>
<p>WHAT:</p>	<p>I want to respond to my clients' need for sustainable transportation of freights; however, I am aware that the shortage of crew and overaged crew poses a major challenge to the efficiency of the logistics chain. Therefore, I am exploring the possibility of using autonomous vessels that require smaller crews and can operate for 24 hours,</p>
<p>WHY:</p>	<p>so that I can increase the efficiency of my operations and remain competitive because I can maintain the customers loyalty and attract new customers.</p>